

Using Visual Attention in a CBIR System

Experimental Results on Landmark and Object Recognition Tasks

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Abstract: Many novel applications in the field of object recognition and pose estimation have been built relying on local invariant features extracted from key points that rely on high-contrast regions of the images. The visual saliency of those regions is not considered by state-of-the-art detection algorithms that assume the user is interested in the whole image. In this paper we present the experimental results of the application of a biologically-inspired model of visual attention to the problem of local feature selection in landmark and object recognition tasks. The results show that the approach improves the accuracy of the classifier in the object recognition task and preserves a good accuracy in the landmark recognition task.

1 INTRODUCTION

Given an image as query, a Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) system returns a list of images ranked according to their visual similarity with the query image. The ranking is based on a comparison among the visual features extracted from the query image and from the images stored in the index. Many CBIR systems support general visual similarity searches based on global features, such as color and edge histograms. The adoption of descriptions based on local features (e.g., SIFT and SURF) provided multimedia information systems with the possibility to build applications able to exploit local image similarities. The number of local visual features extracted from cluttered, real-world images is usually in the order of thousands. When the number is 'too' large, the overall performance of the CBIR system may decline, and, if too many features are extracted from irrelevant regions, the matching accuracy may decline. The reduction of the number of visual features used in the image descriptions can thus be considered a central point in reaching a good overall performance in a CBIR system. In this work we present an approach concerning the application of a biologically-inspired visual attention model for filtering out a subset of the features extracted from an image. The basic assumption of our experimental work is that the user selects the query image according to its most salient areas. In order to assess quantitatively the performance of the approach,

we tested it on a landmark recognition task and an object recognition task using two publicly available datasets. The results show that the feature filtering based on the image saliency is able to drastically reduce the number of keypoints with an improvement or just a slightly decrease in the accuracy of the classifier in, respectively, the object recognition task and the landmark recognition task.

2 PREVIOUS WORKS

(Marques et al., 2007) proposes a segmentation method that exploits visual attention in selecting regions of interest in a CBIR dataset to be used in the similarity computation. The salient regions are used to segment the image with a region growing approach. They compute the visual saliency using the model in (Itti et al., 1998), while another visual attention model, the Stentiford's, is used to guide the segmentation step. They experimented their methods on a dataset containing 110 images of road signs, red soda cans, and emergency triangles. Since that dataset is well known and used in other published experimentations, we used it in order to test our filtering approach.

(Gao and Yang, 2011) propose a method for filtering SIFT keypoints using saliency maps. The authors use two different algorithms for computing the image saliency, the Itti-Koch model (for local-contrast analysis) and a frequency-based method (for global-

contrast analysis) (Hou and Zhang, 2007). The final saliency, corresponding to the sum of the saliency maps computed by the two methods, is used to start a segmentation algorithm based on fuzzy growing. They experimented their method on a dataset composed by 10 classes with more than 10 images per class, extracted from the ALOI image dataset and the Caltech 256 photo gallery. The authors show that their method has a precision that is lower than standard SIFT and comparable to PCA-SIFT, but that it is also much faster, making it suitable for use in CBIR systems.

3 BIOLOGICAL INSPIRATION

When we open our eyes we see a colorful and meaningful three-dimensional world surrounding us. Such visual experience results from a sequence of transformations performed on the light stimuli that starts in our eyes. The light is focused on the retinal surface, then processed and transferred to our thalamus, and finally routed to the cerebral cortex. Earlier computational steps extract basic and non-structured features, while later steps are able to compute complex features, such as, for example, lines at various orientations or different color layouts using a center-surround receptive field. However, the amount of information contained in the patterns of neural activity is still too large for our brain to process in a reasonable amount of time. Evolution has thus endowed humans with a series of attentional filters able to reduce the incoming information.

Several psychological theories have been proposed to explain how a unitary visual perception can arise from distinct computational flows filtered by visual attention. In the "Feature Integration Theory" (FIT), the parallel, preattentive processes build an image representation with respect to a single feature and encode the information in feature maps (color, orientation, spatial frequency, ...). The maps are then combined and their peaks of activity are used to choose the areas to inspect. One of the most influential and detailed models was proposed in (Koch and Ullman, 1985). The computational model used in this work is an extension of the model in (Itti et al., 1998), built upon the theory (Koch and Ullman, 1985).

4 THE MODEL

The input image is first encoded in the Lab color model. The raw L, a, and b values are then used to build the color channels I_I , I_R , I_G , I_B , and

I_Y that correspond, respectively, to intensity, red, green, blue, and yellow. Each channel is encoded in an image pyramid, that allows the model to perform a multiresolution analysis of the input image. Such channels are merged in Feature Contrast Maps (FCMs) using a center-surround representation. The model uses single opponent channels, meaning that it builds a pyramid for each opponent feature: (R, G) , (G, R) , (B, Y) , (Y, B) , (I_{on}, I_{off}) , (I_{off}, I_{on}) , where (f, f^*) denotes a map encoding a center-surround difference with feature f in the center and feature f^* in the surround. For example, the map BY , obtained by I_B and I_Y , is computed as follows: $BY \leftarrow [(B * G_0) - \max(Y * G_1, Y * G_2)]_+$, where $*$ corresponds to the convolution, G_0, G_1, G_2 corresponds to Gaussian kernels with different sizes (G_0 corresponds to the central part of the receptive field, G_1, G_2 to the surround) and the function $[\cdot]_+$ simply sets to zero negative values. The FCMs are then merged into Feature Maps (FMs) that encodes the strength of each couple of opponent features. For example, the maps (R, G) and (G, R) leads to the FM RG . The two FCMs are normalized in order to reduce the values in maps with a diffuse activity and enhance the values in maps with only few and small spots of activity. The normalization is based on the values of Summed Area Tables indicating how the activity is spread all over the map. Local orientation maps are computed on the intensity pyramid by convolving the intensity image in each layer using a set of oriented Gabor filters at four different orientations $\theta \in \{0, \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3}{2}\pi\}$. The filters used in the model implementation are expressed as in (Daugman, 1985), with parameters with biological plausible values (Serre et al., 2007). The two color FMs and the intensity FM are merged together using the same normalization strategy described before. The four orientation maps are merged into a single FM with the same normalization method. All of the maps are then normalized again using the method above and merged together by simply computing the pixel-wise maximum among the maps. For each level of the pyramids, the maps are merged into Level Saliency Maps (LSMs). The final saliency map is obtained at the lowest resolution level by taking the maximum value in the corresponding area in all the LSMs.

5 EXPERIMENTATIONS

We tested the proposed VA-based filtering approach on one landmark recognition and one objection recognition tasks using two different datasets. The first one is the publicly available dataset containing 1227

Figure 1: Accuracy on the the two datasets. Left: PISA-DATASET; Right: STIM-DATASET. Solid line: filtering based on the saliency map; dashed line: random filtering. The maximum accuracy obtained without applying any filter is shown by the horizontal dotted line.

photos of 12 landmarks (object classes) located in Pisa (also used in (Amato et al., 2011; Amato and Falchi, 2011)), hereafter named PISA-DATASET. The dataset is divided in a *training set* (Tr) consisting of 226 photos (20% of the dataset) and a *test set* (Te) consisting of 921 photos (80% of the dataset). The second dataset is contains 258 photos belonging to three classes (cans, road signs, and emergency triangles), hereafter named STIM-DATASET. The dataset is similarly split into a training and a test set containing, respectively, 206 and 52 photos. The experiments were conducted using the Scale Invariant Feature Transformation (SIFT) (Lowe, 2004) algorithm that represents the visual content of an image using scale-invariant local features extracted from regions around selected keypoints. Such keypoints usually lie on high-contrast regions of the image, such as object edges. Image matching is performed by comparing the description of the keypoints in two images searching for matching pairs. The candidate pairs for matches are verified to be consistent with a geometric transformation (e.g., affine or homography) using the RANSAC algorithm (Fischler and Bolles, 1981). The percentage of verified matches is used to argue whether or not the two images contain the very same rigid object. The number of local features in the description of the images is typically in the order of thousands. This results in efficiency issues on comparing the content of two images described with the SIFT descriptors. For this reason we applied a filtering strategy selecting only the SIFT keypoints extracted from regions with a high saliency. Each image in the dataset was processed by the VA model producing a saliency map. Since the resolution of the final saliency map is low, each saliency map has been resized to the dimension of the input image.

PISA-DATASET. In order to study how many SIFT keypoints could be filtered out by the index, we applied several thresholds on the saliency levels stored

in the saliency maps. The thresholds range from 0.3 to 0.7 the maximum saliency value (normalized to 1). The 0.3 threshold did not modify at all any of the saliency maps, meaning that all of the saliency maps had values larger than 0.3. SIFT keypoints were filtered out only when they corresponded to points in the saliency map with a value below the given threshold. In order to see how effective the filtering by the VA model was, we compared it against random filtering. In this second case, we kept from 10% to 90% of the original SIFTs by incrementally removing keypoints chosen randomly. We used *accuracy* in assigning the correct landmark to the test images (in the previously mentioned dataset) as the measure of performance. For each test image, the best candidate match between the training images is selected using the SIFT description and verifying the matches for an affine transformation using the RANSAC algorithm. The results of the experimentation are shown in figure 1. The x-axis shows the percentage of SIFT keypoints kept after filtering. The y-axis corresponds to the accuracy reached by the classifier after the filtering. The maximum accuracy is reached by not removing any keypoint and is equal to 0.935. The accuracy does not vary much till a 40% filtering, when it starts decreasing. When all the saliency values are used, the filtering performed using the visual saliency maps reaches a 0.89 accuracy when it removes almost 57% of the original keypoints. The performance of the VA-based filter is very similar to the random-based one when 30% keypoints are kept. However, when the percentages of removed keypoints increases, the VA-based filtering algorithm outperforms the random filtering. The results of the model with aggressive filtering levels are quite encouraging. The model is in fact able to preserve regions that are relevant for the recognition of the specific object. There is a decrease in the overall accuracy with respect to the SIFT classifiers, but the time needed to perform the classifica-

tion is significantly lower. In fact, when the classification uses 100% of the SIFT keypoints (no filtering), the average time for classifying a single test image is 7.2 seconds. When we use only 30% or 20% of the original SIFT keypoints (VA-based filtering) the time needed for the classification of an image is, respectively, 0.78 and 0.6 seconds per image on average. Even when the random filter and the VA-based filter have the same accuracy, the saliency-based filter provides better keypoints. When only a 40% percentage of the original keypoints is kept, the average time needed to classify a single image is 1.07 and 0.97 seconds for, respectively, images preprocessed using the random filter and the VA-based filter. However, the experimentation has also shown a relevant limitation of filtering approaches based on bottom-up visual attention. In fact, many test images misclassified by the classifier contain salient regions that are radically different from the other images in the same category. For example, since many pictures contain people in front of monuments, the visual attention filter is prone to remove (i.e., assign a low saliency to) the monument in the background and preserve the people as the most salient areas.

STIM-DATASET. In the case of the STIM-DATASET the saliency maps were thresholded using values ranging from 0.1 to 0.9 the maximum value in the map. The percentage of SIFT keypoints kept and used by the classifier ranges from 11% to 77% (on average) the number of keypoints originally extracted from images. In this dataset, the relevant objects are well-separated by the background in almost every image. Furthermore, since they never fill the entire frame, their features are not considered too 'common' and are not suppressed by the attentional mechanism. From the graph shown in Fig. 1 it is clear that the VA-based filtering is able both to improve the accuracy and to decrease the time needed for the classification. By using only half the keypoints selected by the VA model, the classifier reaches 81% accuracy, which is much greater than those obtained using 100% of the original keypoints or 90% randomly selected, that are equal to, respectively, 0.77 and 0.74.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented a filtering approach based on a visual attention model that can be used to improve the performance of CBIR systems and object recognition algorithms. The model uses a richer image representation than other common and well-known models and is able to process a single image in a short time thanks to many approximations

used in various processing steps. The results show that a VA-based filtering approach allows to reach a better accuracy on object recognition tasks where the objects stand out clearly from the background, like in the STIM-DATASET. The results on the PISA-DATASET are encouraging since a faster response in the classification step is obtained with only a minor decrease in accuracy. However, the results need a deeper inspection in order to gain a better understanding of the model on cluttered scene where the object (or landmark) to be detected does not correspond to the most salient image areas and usually fills the frame.

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